
**USING THE WEBQUEST TASK BASED ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF
SPEAKING SKILLS IN 10TH GRADE OF THE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
BOSTONLIK DISTRICT**

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Abstract.

By our Republic was set the new requirements related to the field of education, whether it is teaching and training or learning, must have high quality education at its core and this system needs to be able to meet the demands of the educational system. Internet-resources can be used for a variety of educational purposes. The global network makes it possible for the teachers and the participants to get any necessary information. Students can participate in various contests and Olympiads held on the Internet. It is necessary to mention the opportunity to participate in such events not only at the national level, but also at the whole world level. The reason is that nowadays, a participant who knows a foreign language works easily in the search engine and can re-enter the desired forums and sites. For example, listening to audio tapes in foreign language classes improves the student's listening skills and watching various necessary videos on the Internet network. It helps to understand the phonetic peculiarities of the studied language and to use the acquired knowledge in the speaking process. Learners begin to express their thoughts clearly and correctly in a foreign language.

Key words.

WebQuest, WebQuest technology, WebQuest structure, educational technology, the WebQuest task 'The bad Habits', speaking skills, communicative competence, internet-resources, motivation, creativity.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВЕБ-КВЕСТА НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ РАЗГОВОРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ В 10-М КЛАССЕ СРЕДНИХ ШКОЛ БОСТОНЛИКСКОГО РАЙОНА

Аннотация.

Нашей Республикой были поставлены новые требования, касающиеся сферы образования, будь то преподавание или обучение, в основе которого должно быть качественное образование, и эта система должна быть в состоянии удовлетворить требования образовательной системы. Интернет-ресурсы могут использоваться в различных образовательных целях. Глобальная сеть дает возможность преподавателям и участникам получать любую необходимую информацию. Студенты могут участвовать в различных конкурсах и олимпиадах, проводимых в сети Интернет. Необходимо отметить возможность участия в подобных мероприятиях не только на национальном уровне, но и на уровне всего мира. Причина в том, что в наше время участник, знающий иностранный язык, легко работает в поисковой системе и может повторно зайти на нужные форумы и сайты. Например, прослушивание аудиокассет на занятиях по иностранному языку улучшает навыки аудирования ученика и просмотр различных необходимых видеороликов в сети Интернет. Это помогает понять фонетические особенности изучаемого языка и использовать полученные знания в процессе разговорной речи. Учащиеся начинают четко и правильно выражать свои мысли на иностранном языке.

Ключевые слова.

веб-квест, технология веб-квеста, структура веб-квеста, образовательная технология, задание веб-квеста «Вредные привычки», речевые навыки, коммуникативная компетентность, интернет-ресурсы, мотивация, креативность.

Introduction

"WebQuest" technology, a new method of language learning, cannot be implemented without the Internet. This method increases the motivation to learn languages. General education has several purposes. The most important among them is formation and development of communicative competence. Communicative competence is the ability to communicate and own it. This term is a person's level of skill in communicating with other people. Communicative approach means the ability to communicate and form intercultural relations, which is the basis of the Internet.

WebQuest itself and its tasks are not possible without Internet-resources. Technology requires students to perform tasks independently. Role options and their attributes are defined by the author of this technology and placed on the appropriate page of the website. This technology has a block structure. The elements of this WebQuest structure:

1. Introduction;
2. Task;
3. Process;
4. Resources;
5. Assessment;
6. Conclusion;
7. Used literature;
8. Teacher's page.

WebQuest technology can be considered one of the most effective tools for developing oral speech. This new educational technology was founded in 1995 by American scientists B. Dodge and T. March. Nowadays, this technology is very widespread, not only in the USA and European countries, also they began to be widely used in other continents. So, if we consider how to use this technology in foreign language classes, what will be necessary to introduce it into the lesson:

- Computer class - this allows students to more easily mobilize their creative intellectual potential and learn;
- Internet connection - now all educational institutions have the opportunity to connect to Internet networks, and information technologies provide convenience to students;
- Level of computer literacy – requires computer literacy from teachers and students, because all stages of the educational process are carried out using computers.

It follows that WebQuest technology cannot be implemented without IT technologies, because WebQuest is the use of Internet information resources for a long-term purposeful search to solve any problem or perform a specific task with elements of role-playing games.

Materials And Methods

Using the WebQuest technology, we observe the results of the development of oral speech in English and the impact of experimental work on the quality of lessons among high school students of 3 secondary schools in Bostonlik district in Republic of Uzbekistan. The main goal of this article is to increase speaking and

motivate students in language learning using WebQuest technology in secondary schools. In order to achieve the goal of the research work, pre-post tests were conducted to determine the activities and achievements of students aimed to the development of speaking skills. For experimental work, 214 students from 3 secondary schools of Bostonlik district were selected and divided into groups. The groups were divided into 10th grade and 11th grade, and 1 control group and 1 experimental test group were selected from each school. So, the first school was chosen as the № 1 general education school of the district with a total of (81) participants, of which (18) students were in the 10th grade control group, and (21) students were in the 11th grade control group. 10th grade (41) students and 11th grade (40) students participated in the WebQuest test groups. As the second school, general education school № 54 in the district was chosen, and a total of (53) students were selected in this school, and from them (18) 10th grade control group (18) students were involved in the pilot test, in 11th grades (8) were selected for the control group and (9) for the experimental group. The third school was selected as the District Specialized School, and 10th grade (21) general students and 11th grade (19) general students were observed as control and experimental groups.

In the experimental work conducted for the development of speaking skills using WebQuest technology, the upper grades of secondary schools were selected, and the students were 15-16 years old, and they studied English lessons from the 1st grade. Research work has set goals and tasks and focused on solving them, tasks:

- Identifying and comparing differences between the control and experimental groups in the development of speaking skills;
- Determining the speaking achievement differences between experimental groups in 3 selected secondary schools.

Thus, the WebQuest technology, like any educational technology, has an invariant part expressed by the elements of the structure and the content filling requirements reflected in the technological map. To improve the quality of the education system, it is necessary to integrate modern informational-pedagogical and traditional technologies in the educational process. This concept of technology can be understood as the idea of organizing independent activities of students, they are designed for the development of personality in the team using navigators and instructions, and tips, Internet-resources in solving the main problems through performing additional tasks. It is necessary to create a positive environment in the implementation of technology both in classes and in extracurricular activities, to

encourage students for independent research and creativity, and to create conditions.

The chosen topic of the research WebQuest task was 'The Bad Habits', it was created according the 10th grades new English book 'Prepare'. The WebQuest task is organized differently from the basic WebQuest structure and includes:

- Introduction;
- Karaoke time;
- Task;
- Process;
- Roles;
- Resources;
- Questions;
- Practice;
- Project work;
- Evaluation;
- Conclusion.

This WebQuest, like the previous 10th grade WebQuest, was created on BookWidgets.com.

The "Stop Bad Habits" WebQuest task for 10th grade students is an experimental process work.

The second WebQuest task was considered to be the second stage of tests, with experimental work continuing in Bostonlik district secondary schools. This WebQuest was devoted to the most serious vices and habits among young people today, namely, drinking alcohol, smoking tobacco, and taking narcotic-psychootropic substances. The main purpose of the WebQuest task was to teach and explain to the students that there is only a negative side to these vices, and if there are those who have strayed into it, to turn them away and to walk away from such things. This WebQuest task was also short and was conducted and observed in 5 lesson processes for practical lessons.

In addition to the educational aspects of this task, the WebQuest task develops many skills in students, especially speaking, reading, listening, and high-level thinking skills in Bloom's taxonomy, analyzing and synthesizing, evaluating, and develops creativity.

Results And Discussion

The results of this work show that the Internet connection makes educational processes interactive with the help of WebQuest technology. One of the

requirements of the educational system of our modern age allows students and teachers to use technologies effectively in the course of their lessons. Students are required to use the necessary information, gadgets and computer in the Internet networks, not only in the course of lessons.

The results of the article showed that the tasks created in WebQuest helped students to develop their motivation and speaking skills. WebQuest tasks were identified through recent interviews with them, and many students reported that teaching using WebQuest technology was fun and unique, and students learned new words for themselves. words, phrases and new concepts through links in WebQuest task and expanded their knowledge and world views. There are tasks and Internet-resources in WebQuest technology, suitable for students' learning types (kinesthetic/auditory/visual), which makes WebQuest technology unique.

WebQuest is not only useful for students to learn, but also useful for teachers, because students work in the process of the lesson, and teachers only perform the duties of observers and instructors. During the experimental lesson process, the students learned using real materials, they study the world in one classroom without having to go anywhere.

The main goal of modern education is the active use of various methods and their forms in the processes of receiving and imparting education, making it easier for students to acquire knowledge. WebQuest technology makes it easier to search for information needed to perform tasks and helps to use sources for obtaining various information. Additionally, WebQuest can develop students' skills such as remembering information, critical thinking, finding solutions to problems, and planning themselves in completing tasks. Therefore, the use of computer technologies in education improves the processes of learning by providing new opportunities in the teaching process.

Also, in the results of monitoring the most experiments of WebQuest technology, there were found that the use of Internet networks in teaching processes can be some expensive. Because when using WebQuest technology, students are required to use Internet connection techniques to complete it, which prevents the teaching process to be carried out unequally. There are also schools and students with limited funds who may not be able to afford computers and gadgets. Similar problems were observed in the process of experimental work. Not all students could use the Internet connection at the same time, because most of them did not have an Internet connection on their mobile devices, and they used Internet networks only through the WI-FI connection at their homes.

But despite these problems, the use of the Internet is the need of the time, and it is necessary to use it, because the volume of information on it is unlimited. It is the responsibility of the teachers and the school administration to create the conditions for using the Internet in the course of the lesson and to use it purposefully. Using WebQuest technology makes teaching processes interesting and fun. In the next paragraph, the results of the experimental tests and their monitoring will be introduced. In it the mathematical calculations were obtained and analyzed with general results from the books.

The WebQuest tasks performed by the students in the experimental work was evaluated based on the clear evaluation criteria. It was evaluated with 3 different points, i.e., 3 points is an excellent rating, 2 points is a good rating, and 1 point is a satisfactory rating. Evaluation criteria are given for each WebQuest task, based on which we will mention general evaluation criteria, that is:

- 3 points – awarded to students who actively participated in all stages of the WebQuest task and show their speaking skills well;
- 2 points – awarded to students who were able to participate in WebQuest tasks and spoke a little about the given tasks;
- 1 point – awarded to students who could not fully participate in the WebQuest tasks, or could not complete the speaking skills tasks.

Table 1.

Indicators of the results of the experimental and control groups after the experimental works:

Schools and grades	№1 school		№2 school		№3 school		Total
	10-grade	11-grade	10-grade	11-grade	10-grade	11-grade	
Experimental group participants	23	19	21	19	18	9	109
A1	2	2	1	2	3	2	12
A2	9	7	5	7	9	5	42
B1	9	8	11	7	4	2	41
B2	3	2	4	3	4	0	14
Control group participants	18	21	21	19	18	8	105
A1	5	7	5	3	6	2	28
A2	9	8	8	8	10	4	47
B1	3	6	6	6	2	2	25
B2	1	0	2	2	0	0	5

Conclusion

Along with the positive aspects of using WebQuest technology, it was observed also the problematic aspects in the process of experimental work. As said above that is conducting the lesson process with WebQuest-technology makes the educational process expensive in terms of money and it leads to inequality. Because all secondary schools and all students may not be able to conduct classes using the Internet and computers.

One more time these problems are the responsibility of individuals and organizations responsible for educational processes, that is necessary to provide schools with computers and Internet connection.

Here are the aspects and recommendations for teachers need to know in order to use WebQuest technology:

- It is necessary for teachers to have Internet and computer literacy;
- Creating a WebQuest task takes a long time and teachers are required to be creative;
- Teachers need to know how to use links when working with resources and to know how to analyze and sort huge amounts of Internet-resources;

- When choosing the topic and tasks of the WebQuest, teachers should make it compatible with the topics and tasks in the students' textbooks;
 - When using the WebQuest task, it is requested to create an environment in which students need to work in the center during the lesson processes;
- Teachers can create WebQuests for students and maintain them for years by checking the resources section regularly.

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